

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KILAMA****FIRST NAME: FELIX DOUGLAS****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: MS Office Standard 2010 on Windows 10)

List 5 to 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Starting the essay (EUCLID 2021, 7-8)
2. Writing the essay (EUCLID 2021, 10-11)
3. Punctuations (EUCLID 2021, 15-23)
4. American versus British English (EUCLID 2021, 24-32)
5. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

In this Response Paper, I discuss academic essay writing based on my understanding of the ACA-491D Coursepack for Period One. I use examples from the coursepack to illustrate my argument to that effect. After conducting a critical reading of the coursepack, I can define academic essay writing as a structured form of writing conducted by students or researchers for academic purposes. An academic essay aims at responding to specific theories or hypotheses about a research subject. As a beginner, the study material mentioned above offers me the fundamentals of scholarly writing. It provides guidelines on choosing a topic, starting writing, organizing references, editing, and submitting my essay to the course instructor. The material also presents guidelines for the writing process. It explains how to use punctuation marks correctly, differentiate between American and British English, and suggests consistency in using one particular variant of English in my response. I present my response to five concepts from the study material for the paper. Namely: Starting the essay, writing the essay, punctuations, comparing American and British English and plagiarism.

2) STARTING THE ESSAY

Although academic essay writing is not restricted to being conducted in a particular order, some course of action must be considered when starting to write. These steps include starting with it early enough to avoid rushing the work, avoiding stress, and making unnecessary mistakes. An early start is crucial because it allows me to think before putting my thoughts into writing. It gives enough time to consult relevant literature on the topic and re-envision it to improve the draft. Therefore, I will start drafting my dissertation early enough to give me “enough time to read, research the topic, think and write” (EUCLID 2021, 7). I have already drafted my concept paper, made initial plan and defined the key milestones in my Doctorate program as a sketch that I will improve on rather than starting from scratch.

The pyramid of Figure 1, on page 8 of the coursepack, summarizes the essential steps in writing an essay, from analyzing the questions and defining critical terms to the last step, where the essay is finally submitted to the course instructor (EUCLID 2021, 8). The repetition of drafting, editing, and redrafting underscores the need to refine the essay to the utmost level before handing it in. The idea of seeking the support of a colleague or friend to read my work helps me to get feedback and input from a different perspective. It enriches my writing with diversity since the colleague may appreciate the work from a different angle of argument about the subject.

After reading the ACA-401D Period 1 Coursepack, I recognized some gaps in my draft concept paper. Like Cleenewerck and Gulma underline the importance of identifying and diagnosing the real issue that an academic study intends to address (2021, 7), I established a hypothetical research proposal framework. I then composed them into texts and asked leading questions the study sought to answer. I even carried out a literature review to search for facts relevant to the research topic. However, much as I thought I wrote an outstanding concept, I ascertained that I did not express some answers to research questions as they should have been in an academic writing after reading the course material. I will work towards bridging the gaps I identified in concept while undertaking periods one to six of the course.

3) WRITING THE ESSAY

A structure and framework are like the network of bones that make up the body’s skeleton. Therefore, the first draft is like a skeleton that needs to be filled with more “flesh” by adding new factual information as I read additional relevant literature. Therefore, the graphical presentation of the format of an essay on page 10 of the coursepack provides a summary of the main structure of academic writing. The structure includes an introduction, a body, and a conclusion. However, each part of the structure must flow smoothly into the next one, giving the text an easy transition from one part to another (EUCLID 2021, 10). The smooth changes from one paragraph to another, with detailed explanations of concepts, add substance and content to the framework. The

arrangement of paragraphs and sentences in logical sequences enhances the flow that eases reading and captures the reader's attention to the essay.

The introduction part of an academic essay concisely conveys vital information about my topic to the reader. Here, I present the topic with a broad opening sentence, stipulate my problem statement, and briefly introduce answers that the research questions solicit. It is also a section in the essay where I outline my strategy to achieve my objectives (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 10). My aim in a particular study is to search for empirical evidence corroborating or disagreeing with my theories to inform attempts towards addressing a targeted problem. In the introduction, I provide an overview of the topics or areas of study that my essay intends to discuss.

The body is the structure section where I develop my argument by answering the research questions. Here, I demonstrate my knowledge and understanding of the relevant books I have read in pursuit of the study and elucidate all critical areas within the topic using facts from such relevant pieces of literature to develop my argument (EUCLID 2021, 10). I can develop sentences supporting my argument from reliable sources. My trusted sources include textbooks, journals, policy documents, international legal instruments, and other pertinent literature on the same field or topics related to my subject of study. The information, ideas, and words I get from these sources must be appropriately cited, either through quotations or paraphrasing. The body of my scholarly paper can be composed of two or more parts depending on the number of research questions it intends to answer.

In conclusion, I summarize critical arguments from the essay's main body. However, I do this without introducing new ideas or concepts that I have not discussed in the body of the essay (EUCLID 2021, 10). Here, I outline answers to research questions and present concise analyses of key findings. Since academic writing seeks to contribute to the original knowledge for policy and scholarly consumption, I can also make critical recommendations to concerned authorities in this part. Equally crucial under this section are the suggestions for further research in the same or similar areas to scholars.

4) PUNCTUATIONS

Punctuation marks that I reviewed in the coursepack include apostrophes, brackets, bullet points, commas, ellipsis, hyphen, colon, semi colon, full stop, quotation mark, exclamation mark, and question marks. However, I will only discuss a few for this report and elaborate on their importance to academic writing.

Wabwire Joseph summarizes the importance of punctuation to a scholar in his book Fountain Core English Grammar when he says: "A writer who makes proper use of the punctuation marks is like a careful driver who makes proper use of indicators and signals" (2007, 190). A writer cannot work without correctly using punctuation marks, and a sentence that is not adequately punctuated is intelligible. The lack of punctuation in a sentence makes it incomplete. Improper punctuation can either change the intended meaning of a phrase or mislead the reader to assume its meaning. A person reading a

wrongly punctuated work can only guess what it means and, therefore, finds it incomprehensible. The correct application of punctuation marks gives one the right direction to the meaning of a sentence or statement. For instance, when one incorrectly uses a particular form of end mark, whether a period, a question mark, or an exclamation mark in a sentence, it will change its entire meaning. That is to say; when I make an interrogative sentence and put an exclamation at the end instead of a question mark, the whole sentence will change into an exclamatory sentence. For instance, if I send an email to my work supervisor to confirm with him my report thus: “No big deal about it!” instead of ending it with a question mark, “No big deal about it?” My supervisor might assume that I have already decided that there is no problem with the report and that his comments are unnecessary.

Another essential punctuation mark in writing is a Comma. Commas are used to separate principal clauses that are too long. Such clauses are usually joined by conjunctions such as yet, as, and, but, or, and so on. “In writing, the comma is used in the same way a motorist uses break lights or hand signals to alert other road users that he or she is stopping or turning left or right, hence calling upon them to slow down.” (Wabwire 2007, 195). Therefore, commas are for pauses in sentences. They allow the reader to rest and breathe before continuing with reading. Commas are also used to separate items in a list, such as adjectives (yellow, tall, ugly, large, long), verbs (go, walk, talk, play, be), and nouns.

5) AMERICAN AND BRITISH ENGLISH COMPARED

As discussed in writing the essay, logical sequencing makes a piece of writing captivating to the reader and adds fluency to the essay. In order to consistently be fluent, one has to be consistent with the version of English chosen. This requires one to understand the variants of the English language and choose a specific one to use in the essay. This will also make the prose coherent.

The differences between standard American English (SAE) and British English are in the following areas: pronunciation, spelling, grammar, structuring of dates, punctuation, and use of collective nouns, among others. However, “American and British English are both variants of the World English. As such, they are more similar than different, especially with ‘educated’ or ‘scientific’ English” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 25). Choosing a particular variant (American or British) in an essay will also determine the punctuation marks one can use and maintain coherence. The main differences in punctuation are seen primarily in applying commas, periods, and quotation marks in one’s writing. For instance, in quoting a sentence or word, ‘inverted commas’ are used in British English, while “quotation marks” are used in American English.

Some words in American English vary in pronunciation from British English but have the exact spelling. Such words include advertisement, ate, clerk, controversy, dance, dynasty, laboratory, leisure, migratory, secretary, and schedule, to name but a few. The difference in pronunciation does not have much effect on my writing skills. However, variance in spelling, although the same pronunciation, can significantly affect an essay.

This variation can affect my written work because my prose can be confusing if I mix them up. For example, if I use the words tire, defense, and license interchangeably with tyre, defence, and licence, respectively, in a scholarly work. A reader who strictly speaks one variant of English can find my work incoherent. Similarly, my writing can also be incomprehensible if I muddle the application of the same terms, with different but similar spelling and pronunciations, like aluminum, polyethylene, and rise, to interchange them with aluminium, polyethylene, and raise (EUCLID 2021, 25- 26).

There are also other factors like regional variation, education, and ethnic background that have not only influenced dissimilarities between American and British English but also, within the same countries, some variations are due to regions and race. There are versions of English peculiar to a specific region, ethnicity, or social group. For instance, the pronunciation and grammar construction of the English language for Black or African Americans is slightly different from for White Americans. Similarly, the pronunciation of some words from a person born and raised in the northern part of the United Kingdom, like Lancashire, differs from that of one originating from London in the Southeastern. Examples of words like bath, dance, grass, trap, and dance are pronounced differently in the South and North of the United Kingdom (Hughes, Trudgil, and Watt Dominic 2012, 60-63). Level of education and its lack thereof also affects one's diction. This, in turn, affects the content of an essay that he or she writes. It is an aspect that may or may not affect the way that I express my ideas in this Response Paper. My background as an African who is using English as a second language might be depicted in the paper. This, however, may not be readily noticeable since I come from a country where British English is not only the official language but also a principal method of instruction and communication in schools and institutions of higher learning.

6) PLAGIARISM

My credibility is always paramount whenever I am undertaking any academic work. I constantly show those who read my academic essays that I have researched adequately. This feeling to continually uphold my integrity leads me to continuously cite my sources of information to avoid being perceived by my readers as a plagiarist. Plagiarism is when a writer uses a source of information or idea without crediting the author of that information. For example, copying an author's words and using them in your work without crediting him or her (EUCLID 2021, 34). A citation will show the reader where the writer got the information or idea. In this course, ACA-401D, I will use in-text citations to avoid plagiarism. I can either quote the exact words of the author or paraphrase them. However, if I am quoting, I must use quotation marks to capture what the author has said. Quotation can be done in two ways. Long quotations that are more than four lines are not punctuated with quotation marks. They are indented following the Turabian rule of style for block quotations.

As I will ensure that I cite all my sources, I will not use too many quotations because it will overcrowd my work and make it look like I am overly dependent on the work of others. Therefore, I will limit it to allow me to develop my original ideas and make personal standpoints. Another alternative is to paraphrase my sources, although

here, my language and style should be different from the author's original but represent accurate information about the original idea. I will not quote information that are universally known to the public that anyone reading will accept as accurate without bothering to check its validity. For instance, 'drug abuse affects mental health.' This is a generally known fact that should not be cited and I will cite them in my essay.

7) CONCLUSION

An academic essay, or scholarly writing, is factual prose written for academic purposes. They have their own sets of rules and structures guiding them that have to be adhered to by students. As a scholar, I do not have to quote sources merely to show that I have read widely but to develop my argument about the subject I am discussing. Although academic essays do not have a rigid structure, some essential steps have to be strictly followed to achieve it. There are concepts such as punctuation, plagiarism, capitalization, style, citation, and the preferred English variant that one has to be conversant with as a student.

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